

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Article

Advancing Analytical Insights: A review Estimation Techniques for Acebrophylline and Erdostaine

Priya Vadariya*¹, Hiral Popaniya², Dr. Payal Vaja³, Smruti Sankhant⁴, Mihir Makwana⁵

^{1,4,5}Research Schlolar, Faculty of Pharmacy, Dr. Subhash Technical Campus, Junagadh.

^{2,3}Assistant Professor, School of Pharmacy, Dr. Subhash University, Junagadh.

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 16 April. 2025

Keywords:

Acebrophylline, Erdosteine, Ultra Violet, HPLC High Performance Liquid Chromatography, Ultra Performance Liquid Chromatography.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.15226996

ABSTRACT

The present review provides a comprehensive overview of the various analytical techniques used for the estimation of Acebrophylline and Erdosteine, two therapeutic agents primarily used in the management of respiratory disorders. Acebrophylline, a bronchodilator and anti-inflammatory agent, and Erdosteine, a mucolytic, have gained prominence in respiratory care. Accurate quantification of these drugs in bulk, pharmaceutical formulations, and biological matrices is crucial for quality control and pharmacokinetic studies. This review explores diverse analytical methods, including spectroscopic techniques (UV) chromatographic methods (HPLC, UPLC, TLC), and, highlighting their advantages, limitations, and applications. Special emphasis is placed on recent advancements such as green analytical chemistry approaches and stability-indicating methods. The review also discusses method validation parameters in accordance with ICH guidelines, including precision, accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity. This paper aims to serve as a reference guide for researchers and pharmaceutical analysts in developing robust methods for the routine analysis of Acebrophylline and Erdosteine.

INTRODUCTION

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is a progressive lung disorder characterized by declining respiratory function and accompanied by various mental and physical comorbidities. It pose a major global health challenge, significantly

impacting populations worldwide ^[1]. The condition significantly contributes to both illness and death, particularly in developing countries, while also placing a heavy strain on healthcare systems and leading to substantial global healthcare expenditures ^[2]. Chronic obstructive

*Corresponding Author: Priya Vadariya

Address: Research Schlolar, Faculty of Pharmacy, Dr. Subhash Technical Campus, Junagadh.

Email : vadariyapriya@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

pulmonary disease (COPD) is a major global health concern, affecting more than 300 million individuals worldwide and causing approximately 2.9 million deaths annually. By 2040, COPD-related deaths are projected to increase by 32% to 4.4 million per year, elevating it from the ninth to the fourth leading cause of mortality, following ischemic heart disease, stroke and pneumonia^[3]. The World Health Organization (WHO) reports that ambient air pollution is responsible for 4.2 million deaths annually, while 3.8 million deaths are attributed to exposure to biomass fuel and inefficient stoves. Alarming,

WHO estimates that 91% of the global population resides in regions where air quality fails to meet acceptable health standards^[4]. The primary objective of pharmacologic therapy for COPD is to alleviate symptoms, enhance overall health status and exercise capacity, and prevent exacerbations. Although treatment plans are individualized based on each patient's needs, most maintenance therapies can be categorized into three main groups: inhaled corticosteroids, long-acting muscarinic antagonists (LAMA), and long-acting β_2 -agonists^[5].

Figure 1. The Lungs and Chronic Obstructive pulmonary Disease (COPD)^[6].

Classification of (COPD): Major 3 type

Centriacinar COPD: Centriacinar COPD is the most common type of pulmonary COPD, primarily affecting the second and third respiratory bronchioles. The degree of lung tissue destruction varies between lobules. This form of COPD is strongly linked to cigarette smoking and dust inhalation, as evidenced by research dating back to the mid-20th century. Notably, the majority of COPD cases in heavy smokers are of the centriacinar type^[7].

Panacinar COPD: In panacinar COPD, two types of disease distribution have been identified. a) Localized form- This type of COPD exhibits a multilobular distribution, indicating that the disease-related changes are present in multiple lobules. However, the areas of lung damage remain relatively localized within specific regions of the lung. b) Diffuse form- This form of the disease is not restricted to specific zones of the lung's anatomy and can manifest more uniformly across the lung. Unlike localized forms, it does not show a preference for particular lung regions. This

distinction is crucial in understanding the severity and extent of lung damage in panacinar COPD. While the localized form involves discrete areas of damage [8].

Distal acinar COPD: It is a subtype of COPD, The Disease characterized by the enlargement of airspaces at the periphery of the acini. It is typically localized and most frequently observed along the dorsal surface of the upper lungs. This condition is often linked to fibrosis and may coexist with other COPD types. Although usually asymptomatic, distal acinar COPD is recognized as a potential cause of spontaneous pneumothorax, particularly in young adults, as demonstrated in studies by Peters et al, (1978) and Lesur et al (1990)[9].

Pathophysiology of COPD: The development of COPD involves various processes, with a key factor being the imbalance between protease and antiprotease activity, which results in the breakdown of alveolar walls. The details of this mechanism are outlined below.

Protease-Antiprotease Imbalance: Proteases are enzymes responsible for breaking down proteins, while antiproteases serve as their inhibitors. Maintaining a balance between these two is essential for preserving lung tissue integrity. In COPD, this equilibrium is disrupted, leading to increased protease activity. The excessive protease activity causes damage to the alveoli, contributing to the disease's progression.

Reduced antiprotease activity: One of the most crucial antiproteases in the lung is alpha-1 antitrypsin (AAT), which inhibits elastase, a protease that degrades elastin, a vital component of alveolar walls. The pathogenesis of COPD is driven by various processes, with a key factor being

the imbalance between protease and antiprotease activity. The imbalance ultimately results in the destruction of alveolar walls [10]. Repeated exposure of the lungs to harmful substances like tobacco triggers an inflammatory response. While initially protective, prolonged exposure leads to chronic inflammation, causing lung damage such as emphysema and fibrosis. This results in air trapping, reduced airflow, and conditions like COPD. Reducing exposure to harmful substances is crucial for lung health [11].

Parenchymal Destruction and Emphysema: In emphysema the breakdown of alveolar walls causes parenchymal destruction and loss of lung elastic recoil, hindering full exhalation. Combined with airway inflammation, this airflow limitation makes efficient breathing increasingly difficult [12].

Air Trapping and Hyperinflation: Narrow airways and lost elasticity trap air during exhalation, causing lung hyperinflation. This limits fresh air intake, especially during exercise when oxygen demand increases.

Dyspnea and Exercise Limitation: This sequence of events illustrates why COPD patients often develop worsening breathlessness over time, making it increasingly difficult to perform daily activities as the disease advances. Hypoxic vasoconstriction in small pulmonary arteries results in intimal hyperplasia and smooth muscle hypertrophy, which contribute to pulmonary hypertension. The progression of pulmonary hypertension leads to right ventricular hypertrophy and ultimately causes right-sided heart failure [13].

COPD Diagnosis-Symptoms: It is recommended to universally measure COPD symptoms using tools like the COPD Assessment Test (CAT) and the modified Medical Research Council (mMRC)

dyspnea scale, alongside assessing airflow limitation and exacerbation history.

a) **CAT:** An 8 item questionnaire assessing the impact of COPD on health, including cough, phlegm, chest tightness and breathlessness.

b) **mMRC Dyspnea Scale:** Measures breathlessness severity, from exertion to interference with daily activities [14].

Category A: Patients with mild symptoms and low exacerbation risk. Early lifestyle changes, like smoking cessation, can improve outcomes significantly.

Category B: Patients with more symptoms but low exacerbation risk.

Category C: Patients with fewer symptoms but higher exacerbation risk.

Category D: Patients with severe symptoms and high exacerbation.

The categories help clinical tailor treatment to each group's needs, improving prognosis and reducing the burden of COPD [15].

Treatment: The true prevalence of COPD is likely higher than reported, as many case go undiagnosed due to early symptoms being mistaken for aging factor. This underreporting and under treatment pose major public health challenges.

Table 1: Treatment of COPD

Drug name	Class of drug	Therapeutic use
Salbutamol	Bronchodilator	Asthma, COPD, Bronchitis, Cystic fibrosis
Formoterol	Long-acting β_2 Adrenergic Receptor	Increase air flow, Reducing cough
Theophylline	Methylxanthines	Anti-inflammatory Effect
Oral steroids ^[16]	Corticoids	Respiratory, Immunosuppressive
Ampicillin	Betalactum antibiotic	Respiratory, Urinary tract, Gastrointestinal
Amoxicillin	Betalactum antibiotic	Respiratory, Urinary tract, Skin, Dental
Azithromycin	Macrolide antibiotic	Acute bronchitis
Benzyl Penicillin	Natural penicillin	COPD, Bronchitis
Cefotaxime	Cephalosporin	Respiratory, Skin, Urinary Tract
Gentamicin ^[17]	Aminoglycoside	COPD, Bacterial infection

Acebrophylline, a bronchodilator with anti-inflammatory and mucoregulating properties, combines ambroxol and theophylline-7 acetic acid. It is used to treat respiratory disorders like asthma and COPD. Ambroxol, a mucolytic agent, enhances lung function by promoting pulmonary surfactant production, reducing alveolar surface tension. Theophylline-7-acetic acid relaxes airway smooth muscles, improving airflow [18]. The bronchodilator effect of Theophylline-7-acetate stems from its inhibition of intracellular phosphodiesterases, which raises cyclic adenosine

breathing in respiratory conditions [19]. Ambroxol enhances mucociliary clearance by stimulating cilia motility, aiding in effective mucus removal. This dual action reduces congestion and alleviates respiratory symptoms [20]. Acebrophylline inhibits phospholipase A and phosphatidylcholine, key enzymes in producing pro-inflammatory substances like leukotrienes and tumor necrosis factor. By reducing these mediators, it minimizes airway inflammation, a primary cause of obstruction in conditions like

asthma and COPD. This anti-inflammatory effect improves airflow and helps manage chronic symptoms [21].

Figure 2: Structure of Acebrophylline [22]

Mechanism of action: Acebrophylline, containing ambroxol and theophylline-7 acetic acid, works together to support pulmonary surfactant production, regulate mucus and improve mucokinetics for clearing excess mucus. Its anti-inflammatory and antireactive effects help reduce bronchial obstruction, benefiting patients [23].

Mucoregulating action: a) Direct activity (Mucoregulation): The ambroxol in acebrophylline normalizes the viscosity of abnormal bronchial secretions. It works not on the already secreted mucus but by regulating glandular function. Ambroxol helps restore normal mucus production by allowing mucosal cysts to regress and activating serous glands to produce higher Quality mucus, improving overall mucus clearance [24]. b) Indirect activity (Surfactant stimulation): Acebrophylline reduces mucus viscosity indirectly by stimulating alveolar surfactant production. The interaction between mucus and surfactant molecules, particularly bronchial phospholipids, contributes to the formation of the fibrillary structure of mucus. For

mucus to form the supracillary colloidal gel, it must pass through the sol layer and the phospholipid layer [25].

Mucosecretory activity: The results showed that acebrophylline was more effective than ambroxol alone in stimulating mucus secretion. This was confirmed by comparing the 50% effective dose (ED50), which represents the amount needed to achieve half of the maximum effect. Acebrophylline had a significantly lower ED50 of 0.278 Mm/kg, compared to ambroxol's 0.498 mM/kg. This suggests that acebrophylline is more potent in enhancing mucus production at lower oral doses [26].

Anti-inflammatory-antireactive activity: Acebrophylline inhibits phospholipase A₂ in the lung parenchyma, preserving phosphatidylcholine for surfactant resynthesis by type ii pneumocytes Scaglione. Demonstrated in cultured human type ii pneumocytes that acebrophylline significantly reduces LTB₄ leukotriene production, promoting surfactant synthesis. In vivo rat studies further showed reduced LTC₄ and LTB₄ levels after

acebrophylline pretreatment and bronchial lavage, with a notable decrease in LTB₄ compared to controls [27].

Pharmacokinetic of Acebrophylline: This passage outline the pharmacokinetics of acebrophylline in healthy volunteers after a 200mg oral dose. The drug contains two components ambroxol and theophylline-7 acetic acid. Following ingestion, both components are released in the stomach and absorbed through the stomach and intestine [28]. the low blood levels of theophylline-7 acetic acid in acebrophylline suggest that it is unlikely to cause the adverse effects typically associated with theophylline, which occur within a therapeutic window of 10-20 mcg/ml. this indicates that acebrophylline presents a significantly lower risk for such side effects compared to theophylline [29]. Erdostaine, a mucolytic drug (N-(carboxymethylthioacetyl)-homocysteine thiolactone), improves sputum viscosity, relieves cough symptoms in COPD, and enhances antibiotic penetration, increasing their effectiveness [30]. Erdostaine lacks a free thiol group in its original form. However, upon metabolism in vivo. It produce active metabolism containing thiol groups. These metabolites can break disulphide bones in mucins, reducing sputum viscosity and enhancing mucociliary clearance in the airways. Further more, they neutralize anti-inflammatory properties [31]. A novel ultra-high performance liquid chromatography (UHPLC) method has been development to quantify erdosteine and its five impurities, including HCT, N – thiodiglycolyl homocysteine, bis –N-(2-oxo-3-tetrahydrothienylthiodiglycolylamide, and two oxidative degradation products (ox1 and ox2) specifically in newly formulated efferevescent tablets[32]. Two acid degradation products of Erdostaine ,HCT and 2,2 sulfanediyldiacetic acid

have been identification. Various analytical techniques, including HPLC, are reported for determining erdosteine in bulk drugs, formulation and biological sample [33].

Figure 3: Structure of Erdostaine

Mechanism of action: Erdostaine, a mucolytic prodrug, aids in breaking down mucus for easier expulsion from the respiratory tract. It became active after metabolism, releasing two sulphur atoms one from thio-ether in the side chain and another from the thiolactone ring. These free sulphur atoms provide antioxidant effects. Reduce bacterial adhesion, and improve mucociliary clearance. The drug is stable in dry and acidic environments, protecting it during oral administration. Upon reaching the alkaline intestines, its thiolactone ring pens, forming the active metabolite N-thiodiglycolylhomocysteine with a free thiol group. This group breaks disulfide bonds in mucins, reducing mucus viscosity, improving clearance and aiding in respiratory conditions with mucus build up [34].

Pharmacokinetic of Erdosteine: Erdosteine is a mucolytic used in COPD and bronchitis. Its pharmacokinetics include absorption, metabolism, distribution and elimination.

Absorbance: Rapidly absorbed orally, with low bioavailability in its original form. It is metabolized in to the active metabolite, which is pharmacology active.

Metabolism: Undergoes extensive first-pass metabolism in the liver, producing active metabolites. Peak plasma levels are reached 1-2 hours post-administration.

Distribution: Erdosteine and its metabolites are widely distributed in tissues, with 64-70% protein binding to plasma proteins.

Elimination: The active metabolite has a half-life of 1.5-2 hours. About 60-80% is excreted in urine, with a smaller portion in feces [35].

Table 2: Physicochemical Properties of Acebrophylline and Erdostaine

Parameters	Description	
Drug name	Acebrophylline	Erdostaine
Category of drug	FDC	FDC
Class of drug	Bronchodilator (β -2 adrenergic)	Mucolytic agent (β -2 adrenergic)
CAS Number	96989-76-3	84611-23-4
Physical Appearance	White to off white	White or Slightly yellowish
Chemical Formula	$C_{22}H_{28}Br_2N_6O_5$	$C_8H_{11}NO_4S_2$
Dosage form of drug	Film coated tablet	Film coated tablet
IUPAC Name of drug	4-[(2-amino-3,dibromophenyl)methylamino]cyclohexan-1-ol;2-(1,3-dimethyl-2,6-dioxopurin-7-yl)acetic	2-([(2-oxothiolan-3yl)carbamoyl]methyl)sulfanyl)acetic
Use of drug	COPD, Chronic bronchitis	COPD, Respiratory
Half-life of drug	4-9hr	3-4hr
Side effect of drug	Nausea, Vomiting, Headache	Skin reaction, allergy

Table 3: The Analytical Method Development & Validation of Acebrophylline

Drug Name	Analytical Method	Description	Ref.
Acebrophylline	UV Spectroscopy	Linearity: Range 2-18 μ g/ml Solvent: Methanol Wavelength: 270nm	36
Acebrophylline	UV Spectroscopy	Linearity: Rang 2-20 μ g/ml Solvent: Ethanol Wavelength: 274nm	37
Acebrophylline	RP-HPLC	Stationary Phase: C18column Mobile Phase: Acetate buffer (4.7pH) Methanol Flow Rate: 0.85 ml Detection: 274nm Concentration Range: 0.5-200 μ g/ml	38
Acebrophylline	HPTLC	Mobile Phase: Toluene and Methanol 5:5v/v Wavelength: 248nm Concentration Rang: 500-2500 μ g/ml	39

Table 4: The Analytical Method Development & Validation of Acebrophylline with Other Drug

Acebrophylline+ Acetylcysteine (Tablet)	RP-HPLC	Stationary Phase: Hypersil, BDS,C18 Mobile Phase: Buffer solution(pH:7),acetonitrile(90:10) Flow Rate: 1.0 ml/min Detection: 260nm(PDA) Concentration Rang: Acebrophylline (200µg/mg) Acetylcysteine (600µg/mg)	40
Acebrophylline+ Acetylcysteine	RP-HPLC	Stationary Phase: Hypersil BDS,C18,100×4.6mm,5µ MobilePhase: BufferPhosphate(pH:6) Acetonitrile (90:10% v/v) Flow Rate: 0.9ml/min Detector: 260nm(PDA) ConcentrationRange: Acebrophylline (25-150µg/ml), Acetylcysteine (150-900µg/ml)	41
Acebrophylline+ Levocetirizine+ Pranlukast	HPLC	StationaryPhase: C18Kinetexcolumn (250mm×4.6mm×5µg) Mobile Phase: Methanol and Acetone (14:86) Flow Rate: 1.0ml/min Concentration Rang: (100-1600µg/ml)	42
Acebrophylline+ Doxofylline (Tablet)	HPTLC	Mobile Phase: Toluene, Methanol, Glacial acetic acid(6:2:2v/v) Wavelength: 232nm Concentration Range: Acebrophylline(100-600µg/ml)	43
Acebrophylline+ Montelukast sodium	HPTLC	Mobile Phase: Chloroform, Ethyalacetate, Methanol, Tryethylamine(6:4.5:2.5:0.8,v/v/v/v) Wavelength: 272nm Concentration Rang: Acebrophylline(600to1000µg/ml), Montelukast sodium(12000-20000µg)	44
Acebrophylline+ Montelukast sodium	HPLC	StationaryPhase: C18Column(Hibar Lichrospher 100, RP- 18e, 5µm, 250mm L ×4.6mm diameter in size MobilePhase: Acetonitrile,Methanol, (60:40% v/v,pH3.2) Flow Rate: 0.8 ml/min Detector: 260nm(UV) ConcentrationRang: Acebrophylline (25µg/ml), Montelukast sodium(100-500µg/ml)	45
Acebrophylline+ Montelukast+ Fexofenadine	RP-HPLC	Stationary Phase: Hyper clone 5µ BDS C18 130A (250×4.6mm) MobilePhase: Methanol,Ammonium, Ortho phosphoric acid (70:30) Flow Rate: 1.0ml/min Detector: 268nm(PDA) ConcentrationRang: Acebrophylline (100-200µg/ml),Montelukast (10µg/ml), Fexofenadine (180µg/ml)	46

Table 5: The Analytical Method Development & Validation of Erdosteine

Drug Name	Analytical Method	Description	Reference
Erdosteine	HPLC	Stationary Phase: C18 column (250mm × 4.6mm, 5µm) Mobile phase: Acetonitrile (0.01 mol/L), Citric acid solution (13:87v) Flow Rate: 1. ml/min Detector: 254nm (PDA) Concentration Rang: 10-80µg/ml	47
Erdosteine	HPLC	Stationary Phase: Ace5-C18 (250×4.6mm) Mobile Phase: Acetonitrile, Phosphate buffer (pH: 7.2) Flow Rate: 0.5ml/min Detector: 236nm(PDA) Concentration Rang: 100µg/ml	48
Erdosteine	UPLC	Stationary Phase: C18-UPLC column 95Å, 2.1×50mm, 1.8µm Mobile Phase: 0.1% Formic acid, Acetonitrile (25:75v/v) Flow Rate: 0.15ml/min Detector: 249nm Concentration Rang: 1-5000µg/ml	49
Erdosteine	UPLC	Stationary Phase: UPLC HSS T3, 1.8µm/ml (2.1mm×150mm) Mobile Phase: 0.1% TFA Water, Methanol Flow Rate: 0.29ml/min Concentration Range: 100µg/ml	50
Erdosteine	UV spectroscopy	Linearity: rang 10-15 µg/ml Solvent: Ethanol Wavelength: 235nm	51

Table 6: The Analytical Method Development & Validation of Erdosteine with Other Drugs

Erdosteine+ Cefixime Trihydrate	HPTLC	Stationary Phase: TLC aluminium plates, silica gel 60F254 Mobile Phase: Ethyl acetate, Acetone Methanol, Water (7.5:2.5:2.5:1.5) Flow Rate: 1.5ml/min Detector: 235nm (UV) Concentration Rang: Erdosteine (100-500µg/ml), Cefixime Trihydrate (150-750µg/ml)	52
Erdosteine+ Cefixime	UPLC	Stationary Phase: Sunfire C18, 5µ, 46mm×150mm Mobile Phase: Buffer (pH:7), Methanol (65:35% v/v) Flow Rate: 1.0 ml/min Detector: 254nm(PDA) Concentration Rang: Erdosteine (20-200µg/ml), Cefixime (30-300µg/ml)	53
Erdosteine+ Cefixime	UV Spectrophotometry	Linearity: Rang 10-15µg/ml Solvent: Ethanol Wavelength: 227.5nm	54

Erdosteine+ Guaiphenesin+ Terbutaline sulphate	HPTLC	Stationary Phase: Aluminium plates, Silica gel 60F254 MobilePhase: Toluene, Dichloromethane, Methanol, Glacialacetic acid (4:4:1.8:0.2% v/v/v/v/) Flow Rate: 2.0nm Detector: 225nm Concentration Rang: Erdosteine(500-300µg/ml), Guaiphenesin(200-1200µg/ml), Terbutaline sulphate (25- 150µg/ml)	55
---	-------	---	----

CONCLUSION:

In the review the conclusion highlights that several analytical method, including Spectrophotometry, chromatography (HPLC, UPLC), have been development and validation for the quantitative analysis of Acebrophylline and Erdosteine individually in perform. These methods are reliable, sensitive, and can be applied for the estimation of these drug in both pure forms and pharmaceutical formulations. The review emphasizes the importance of selecting appropriate methods based on the specific requirements of accuracy, sensitivity, and cost-effectiveness. Future advancements in analytical techniques are perform to combination for (RP-HPLC, HPTLC, UV Spectroscopy and Stability Testing).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS: We are thankful to Dr. Subhash University for providing guidance and supports for this review work.

Abbreviations:

COPD- Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease

UV- Ultra Violet

HPLC- High Performance Liquid Chromatography

TLC- Thin Layer Chromatography

RP-HPLC- Reversed phase High Performance Liquid Chromatography

HPTLC- High Performance Thin Layer Chromatography

cAMP- Cyclic Adenosine Monophosphate

mMRC- Modified Medical Research Council

REFERENCES

1. Rabe KF, Hurd S, Anzueto A, Barnes PJ, Buist SA, Calverley P, Fukuchi Y, Jenkins C, Rodriguez-Roisin R, Van Weel C, Zielinski J. Global strategy for the diagnosis, management, and prevention of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease: GOLD executive summary. American journal of respiratory and critical care medicine. 2007 Sep 15; 176 (6):532-55.
2. Foreman KJ, Marquez N, Dolgert A, Fukutaki K, Fullman N, McGaughey M, Pletcher MA, Smith AE, Tang K, Yuan CW, Brown JC. Forecasting life expectancy, years of life lost, and all-cause and cause-specific mortality for 250 causes of death: reference and alternative scenarios for 2016–40 for 195 countries and territories. The Lancet. 2018 Nov 10; 392 (10159):2052-90.
3. Mathers CD, Loncar D. Projections of global mortality and burden of COPD disease from 2002 to 2030. Plos medicine. 2006 Nov 28; 3(11):e442.
4. Carter P. Environmental health risk assessment for global climate change and atmospheric

- greenhouse gas pollution. *Climate Action*. 2020:413-23.
5. KF R. Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease. Global strategy for the diagnosis, management, and prevention of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease executive summary. *American Journal Respiratory Crit Care Med*. 2007; 176:532-55.
 6. Sawant MP, Padwal LS, Kale SA, Pise NH, Shinde MR. Study of drug prescription pattern among COPD patients admitted to medicine in-patient department of tertiary care hospital. *International Journal of Basic & Clinical Pharmacology*. 2017 September; 6(9):2228-32.
 7. Finkelstein R, Ma HD, Ghezzi H, Whittaker K, Fraser RS, Cosio MG. Morphometry of small Airways in smokers and its relationship to emphysema type and hyperresponsiveness. *American journal of respiratory and critical care medicine*. 1995 July; 152 (1):267-76.
 8. Thurlbeck WM. Chronic airflow obstruction. In *Pathology of the lung*. 1995; 780.
 9. Wiggins J, Strickland B, Turner-Warwick M. Combined cryptogenic fibrosing alveoli is and emphysema: in assessment. *Respiratory medicine*. 1990 Sep 1; 84(5):365-9.
 10. Reid R, Roberts F, MacDuff E. *Pathology illustrated E-book*. Elsevier Health Sciences; 2011 Octamer 24.
 11. Halpin DM, Criner GJ, Papi A, Singh D, Anzueto A, Martinez FJ, Agusti AA, Vogelmeier CF. Global initiative for the diagnosis, management, and prevention of chronic obstructive lungdisease. The 2020 GOLD science committee report on chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *American journal of respiratory and critical care medicine*. 2021 Jan 1; 203(1):24-36.
 12. Friedman PJ. Imaging studies in emphysema. *Proceedings of the American Thoracic Society*. 2008 May 1; 5 (4):494-500.
 13. O'Donnell DE, Laveneziana P. Dyspnea and activity limitation in COPD: mechanical factors. *COPD: Journal of Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease*. 2007 January 1; 4 (3):225-36.
 14. Vander Molen T, Miravittles M, Kocks JW. COPD management: role of symptom assessment in routine clinical practice. *International journal of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease*. 2013 Oct 14:461-71.
 15. Han MK, Muellerova H, Curran-Everett D, Dransfield MT, Washko GR, Regan EA, Bowler RP, Beaty TH, Hokanson JE, Lynch DA, Jones PW. GOLD 2011 disease severity classification in COPD Generation a prospective cohort study. *The lancet Respiratory medicine*. 2013 Mar 1; 1(1):43-50.
 16. Patil S, Patil R, Bhise M, Jadhav A. Respiratory questionnaire-based analysis of awareness of COPD in a large multicenter rural population-based study in India. *Chronic Diseases and Translational Medicine*. 2022 Dec 25; 8 (04):322-30.
 17. Veettil SK, Rajiah K, Kumar S. Study of drug utilization pattern for acute exacerbation of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease in patients attending a government hospital in Kerala, India. *Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care*. 2014 Jul 1;3(3):250-4.
 18. Sravani T, Thota S, Venisetty R, Venumadhav N. RP-HPLC analysis of acebrophylline in gredient capsule dosage form. *Res J pharm*. 2014; 5:480-6.
 19. Tripathi KD. *Essentials of medical pharmacology*. Journal of Physician Medical Ltd; 2013 Sep 30.

20. Bhavik S, Agarwal SK. RP-HPLC Method Development and Validation for Estimation of Acebrophylline. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical Research and Development*. 2018; 6(6):56-9.
21. James J. Estimation of Acebrophylline by HPLC. *Integrated Projects Consortium Experiments*. 2011 August; 25.
22. Saraswathi D, Gigi G, Niraimathi V, Jerad A. Estimation of acebrophylline in pharmaceutical oral solid dosage form by RP-HPLC. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Research* 2010 Jul;9(3):1222-5.
23. Noack w, elbrecht b. Elektronenmikroskopische untersuchungen ueber die wirkung des metaboliten viii von bisolvon auf die foetale rattenlunge (volume 18 & 20).
24. Allegra L, Bossi R, Braga PC. Rheology of bronchial fluids assessed by forced oscillations. *Pulmonary Surfactant System*. Elsevier, Rome. 1983:319-7.
25. Lhermitte M, Lamblin G, Degand P, Roussel P, Mazzuca M. Affinity of bronchial secretion glycoproteins and cells of human bronchial mucosa for Ricinus communis lectins. *Biochimie*. 1977 Oct 12; 59(7):611-20.
26. Pozzi E. Acebrophylline: an airway mucoregulator and anti-inflammatory agent. *Monaldi Archives for Chest Disease*. 2007; 67 (2).
27. Scaglione F, De Martini G, Gattei G. Studi sul meccanismo d'azione di acebrophylline: effect regolatore Sulla produzione di leucotrieni. *Giorn It Mal Tor*. 1992; 1:73-8.
28. Bianchi M, Mantovani A, Erroi A, Dinarello CA, Ghezzi P. Ambroxol inhibits interleukin 1 and tumor necrosis factor production in human mononuclear cells. *Agents and actions*. 1990 November; 31:275-9.
29. Sved S, McGilveray IJ, Beaudoin N. The assay and absorption kinetics of oral theophylline-7-acetic acid in the human. *Biopharmaceutics & drug disposition*. 1981 April 2(2):177-84.
30. Dechant, K.L., & Noble, S. (1996) *Drugs* 52, 875–881. doi:10.2165/00003495-199652060-00009.
31. Braga, P.C., Sasso, M.D., Sala, M.T., & Gianelle, V. (1999) *Arzneimittel forschung* 49, 344–350. Doi: 10.1055/s-0031-1300425.
32. Hohyun K, Kyu YC, Hee JL, Sang BH, Kyung RL. Sensitive determination of Erdosteine in human plasma by use of automated 96-well Solid Phase extraction and LC-MS/MS. *JournalPharma Biomed Annual* 2004; 34: 661-69.
33. Kim ST, Park JS, Tae Kim H, Kim CK. Simple determination of erdosteine in human plasma using high performance liquid chromatography. *Journal of liquid chromatography & related technologies*. 2010 Aug 26; 33 (13):1319-27.
34. Yildirim Z, Sogut S, Odaci E, Iraz M, Ozyurt H, Kotuk M, Akyol O. Oral erdosteine administration attenuates cisplatin-induced renal tubular damage in rats. *Pharmacological Research*. 2003 Feb 1; 47(2):149-56.
35. Liu H, Wang BJ, Yuan GY, Guo RC. RP-HPLC determination of erdosteine in human plasma and its pharmacokinetic studies. *Chinese Journal of Pharmaceutical Analysis*. 2007 October 1; 27(10):1540-3.
36. Patel A, Patil R, Patil S, Sonar KV. Development and Validation of UV Spectroscopic Method for Estimation of Acebrophylline in Tablet Dosage Form.
37. Madhuri s, bhawar HS. A Review on Method Development on Estimation of Acebrophylline and Doxofylline.

38. Dhaneshwar SR, Jagtap VN. Development and Validation of Stability Indicating RP-HPLC-PDA Method for Determination of Acebrophylline and Its Application for Formulation Analysis and Dissolution Study. *Journal Basic and App Science Research*. 2011; 1(11):1884-90.
39. Gandhi SP, Dewani MG, Borole TC, Damle MC. Development and validation of stability indicating HPTLC method for determination of diacerein and aceclofenac as bulk drug and in tablet dosage form. *Journal of Chemistry*. 2012; 9(4):2023-8.
40. Susmita AG, Aruna G, Angalaparameswari S, Padmavathamma M. Simultaneous Estimation of Acebrophylline and Acetylcysteine in Tablet Dosage form by RP-HPLC Method. *Asian Journal of pharmaceutical research*. 2015; 5(3):143-50.
41. Jadhav NS, Lalitha KG. Validated RP-HPLC method development for the simultaneous estimation of acetylcysteine and acebrophylline in capsule formulation. *Journal of Biomedical and Pharmaceutical Research*. 2014; 3(3):10-6.
42. Lohar P, Sharma MK, Sahu AK, Rathod R, Sengupta P. Simultaneous bioanalysis and pharmacokinetic interaction study of acebrophylline, levocetirizine and pranlukast in Sprague-Dawley rats. *Biomedical Chromatography*. 2019 December; 33(12):e4672.
43. Madhuri S, Bhawar HS, Shinde GS. Simultaneous Estimation Method Development and Validation of Acebrophylline and Doxofylline in tablet dosage form by RP-HPLC method.
44. Vekaria HJ, Jat RK. Analytical Method Development and Validation for Simultaneous Estimation of Acebrophylline and Montelukast Sodium in their Pharmaceutical Dosage Form. *Journal of Basic and Applied Scientific Research*. 2011;1(11):1884-90.
45. Thesia UD, Patel PB. Stability Indicating HPLC Method Development for Estimation of Montelukast Sodium and Acebrophylline in Combined Dosage Form. *Inventi Rapid: Pharm Analysis & Quality Assurance* 17 May 2013.
46. Adikay S, Bhavanasi M, Kaveripakam SS. A Stability Indicating RP-HPLC Method for Simultaneous Estimation of Acebrophylline, Montelukast, and Fexofenadine in Bulk Pharmaceutical Dosage Forms. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Investigation*. 2023 April 1; 13(2).
47. Liu H, Xiong X, Wang J, Pei K, Zhong Z, Zhou Z, Cheng Q. Determination, Isolation, and Identification of Related Impurities in Erdosteine Bulk Drug. *Journal of AOAC International*. 2022 May 1; 105(3):696-702.
48. Khan MM, Jain PS, Shirkhedkar AA, Fursule RA, Kale NK, Surana SJ. Stability indicating HPLC determination of Erdosteine in bulk drug and pharmaceutical dosage form. *Journal of pharmaceutical and BioSciences*. 2013 July.
49. Yaman ME, Atila A. A rapid and sensitive UPLC-MS/MS method for quantification of erdosteine as bulk drug and in capsules as dosage forms. *Maced Pharm Bull*. 2021 September 1; 67(2):23-31.
50. Bertolini, T., Vicentini, L., Boschetti, S., & Gatti, R. (2018) *Chromatographia* 81, 1661–1672. Doi: 10.1007/s10337-018-3636-8.
51. RK N, Gaikwad J, Prakash A. Spectrophotometric estimation of erdosteine in pharmaceutical dosage form.
52. Dhoka MV, Gawande VT, Joshi P. Validated HPTLC method for determination of cefixime trihydrate and erdosteine in bulk and combined

- pharmaceutical dosage form. *Eurasian Journal. Analysis Chemistry*. 2011; 8:99-106.
53. Mohanrao, T., Reddy, C.B. and Babu, P.S., 2020. A New Investigational Method for quantification and Validation of Analytical Method for Cefixime and Erdosteine by UPLC with photo diode array Detector in Bulk and Formulation. Application to the Estimation of Product traces. *Indian drugs*, 57(11).
54. Nanda RK, Gaikwad J, Prakash A, Ghosh VK, Nagore DH. Estimation of cefixime and erdosteine in its pharmaceutical dosage form by spectrophotometric method. *Asian Journal of Research in Chemistry*. 2009; 2(4):404-6.
55. Shah PA, Chadhari DP, Mistry NN, Gandhi TR. Development and Validation of HPLC Method for Simulaneous Estimation of Erdosteine, guaphenesin and Terbutaline sulphate using box-Behnken design *India drug* 2017 Dec 1-54(12).

HOW TO CITE: Priya Vadariya*, Hiral Popaniya, Dr. Payal Vaja, Smruti Sankhant, Mihir Makwana, Advancing Analytical Insights: A review Estimation Techniques for Acebrophylline and Erdostaine, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 4, 9274-9287 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15226996>

